

Be Creative in the Pandemic Era : Detecting Types of Snake Bites with Augmented Reality

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Purpose and Background : During this pandemic, there are many things that we are able to do to fill our spare time. Utilizing free time to be creative in making augmented reality-(AR)-based applications is one issue that may change the way we see our world. In addition to having the ability to develop creativity and skill, the AR technology may also be beneficial to the surrounding people, such as in this case to avoid unwanted things regarding venomous snakes. The application of AR in detection of venomous and non-venomous snakes and in guiding first aids after being bitten by a snake is very important, considering the number of snakebites in Indonesia up to one hundred thirty thousand per year with an unknown number of deaths¹. Improper handling resulted in the loss of lives that should have been avoided. Therefore, a required associate application which will share information regarding venomous and non-venomous snakes as well as education first aid for snake bites, can use an application named *ARORAY* which is based on augmented reality technology.

Materials and Methods: Teamwork and general software are needed to support the activities of making this application. Among these software are:

1. 3D designer, using Blender v2.76.
2. 2D designer, using Adobe Illustrator CC 2018.
3. Software engine : version unity 2019.2
4. Social media app, for communication between group members.

We utilized the method of linear sequential model (in software development)². Application design can be made in the form of a storyboard which is entirely the development of collaborative ideas. Then programming is done to translate the design into programming languages (Java and JavaScript), that can be interpreted by the machine. Once the application has been built, the next steps are testing and debugging processes to examine for errors that may exist and to affirm that the desired results are achieved. Within the end, software maintenance is still carried out before and after the software is launched.²

Results and Discussion

Some menus are available in the *ARORAY* application. They provide information about snake species—especially in Indonesia—, differences between venomous and non-venomous snake, and appropriate first aids when someone get bitten by a snake. The following figure shows some snapshots inside of *ARORAY*.

3D Animation

AR Marker Card

To use the application, users need to select an AR snake marker card. Then the selected snake will be visualized. For example, as shown in the above figure, the first snake is a king cobra, which is a venomous snake. The second one is a reticulated python (non-venomous snake). Meanwhile, to see the steps for handling snake bites, the user must scan the AR card first (image of a coconut forest). Then it will appear a 3D animation of a person bitten by a snake and a 'start' menu that contains first aid steps that must be carried out.

In the end, the *ARORAY* application is an educational tool for the Indonesian people to recognize venomous snakes. It will be very beneficial for people who are living in Indonesia to avoid snake bites and how to appropriately handle when get bitten by them. Hopefully this application can be useful and increase our creativity during this pandemic.

REFERENCES

- ¹ Tri Maharani Ahli Toksinologi Indonesia yang Dedikasikan Hidupnya untuk Menangani Kasus Gigitan Hewan Berbahaya from <http://news.unair.ac.id/2020/03/16/tri-maharani-ahli-toksinologi-indonesia-yang-dedikasikan-hidupnya-untuk-menangani-kasus-gigitan-hewan-berbahaya/>
- ² Despa, M. L. (2014). Comparative Study on SoftwareDevelopment Methodologies. Database Systems Journal vol. V,no.3. from <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/339049-analisis-pemilihan-penerapanproyek-meto-b6b1bb1a.pdf>